

Investigation on the Applicability of Hybrid Floating Renewable Energy Structure Systems in Coastal Areas

Büşra CESUR DURMAZ^{1*}

ORCID 1: 0000-0001-9322-8108

ORCID 2: 0000-0001-9517-5388

ORCID 3: 0000-0002-6723-7665

^{1,3} Süleyman Demirel University, Faculty of Engineering and Natural Sciences, Department of Civil Engineering, Isparta, Türkiye.

² Süleyman Demirel University, Faculty of Architecture, Department of Landscape Architecture, Isparta, Türkiye.

* e-mail: busrasesur.pm@gmail.com

Abstract

Renewable energy systems are important technologies that reduce the use of fossil resources and emerged as a solution to the problem of global warming. Today, these technologies are installed both onshore and offshore. In this study, hybrid floating renewable energy structure systems were discussed to meet the energy needs of Türkiye's coastal areas from renewable energy sources. The policies and legislative aspects regarding offshore installations were analysed. In order to implement floating energy structure systems in Türkiye's coastal areas, the features of the floating foundation structure, energy systems and sustainability dimensions were evaluated. The floating energy structure design example proposed in the doctoral thesis "Sustainable Floating Urban Park Model: The Case of Fethiye" was examined. For Türkiye's sustainable energy future, suggestions have been developed for the application of hybrid floating renewable energy structure systems in coastal areas.

Keywords: Coastal areas, floating renewable energy, hybrid energy, floating structure systems, Türkiye.

Kıyı Alanlarında Hibrit Yüzer Yenilenebilir Enerji Yapı Sistemlerinin Uygulanabilirliğine Yönelik İrdeleme

Öz

Yenilenebilir enerji sistemleri, fosil kaynak kullanımını azaltan ve küresel ısınma sorununa çözüm olarak ortaya çıkan önemli teknolojilerdir. Günümüzde bu teknolojiler, hem karada hem de deniz üstünde kurulmaktadır. Çalışmada, Türkiye kıyı alanlarında enerji ihtiyacının yenilenebilir enerji kaynaklarından temin edilebilmesi amacıyla hibrit yüzer yenilenebilir enerji yapı sistemleri ele alınmıştır. Deniz üstü kurulumlarına yönelik izlenen politikalar ve mevzuat boyutları incelenmiştir. Türkiye kıyı alanlarında yüzer enerji yapı sistemlerinin uygulanabilmesi için taşıyıcı temel yapı özellikleri, enerji sistemleri ve sürdürülebilirlik boyutları değerlendirilmiştir. "Sürdürülebilir Yüzer Kent Park Modeli: Fethiye Örneği" doktora tez çalışmasında öneri olarak sunulan yüzer enerji yapı tasarımı örneğinden bahsedilmiştir. Türkiye'nin sürdürülebilir enerji geleceği için hibrit yüzer yenilenebilir enerji yapı sistemlerinin kıyı alanlarında uygulanabilmesine yönelik öneriler geliştirilmiştir.

Anahtar kelimeler: Kıyı alanları, yüzer yenilenebilir enerji, hibrit enerji, yüzer yapı sistemleri, Türkiye.

Citation: Cesur Durmaz, B., Gül, A. & Ay, Z. (2024). Investigation on the applicability of hybrid floating renewable energy structure systems in coastal areas. *Journal of Protected Areas Research*, 3 (2), 178-191.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14544766>

1. Introduction

Coastal areas, which have natural, cultural and social values, are the places where people generally establish their living spaces to meet their primary needs and to engage in various activities such as transport, trade, tourism and industry. Coastal areas are regions where land and sea intersect, have high value in terms of natural structure components, and have been home to human settlements since ancient times (Avcı, 2017). These areas play an important role in ensuring environmental sustainability and strengthening the interaction of societies with nature.

The use of coastal areas is important for agricultural cultivation, animal husbandry, fisheries, forestry activities, natural gas and oil production. In addition, it has versatile advantages in terms of having structural uses for settlement, transportation, industry and defence purposes, meeting the recreation needs of people and becoming tourism destinations (Avcı, 2017). In addition to this, open green space arrangements in coastal areas are becoming important not only for recreation and entertainment purposes but also in terms of environmental sustainability.

However, coastal areas are sensitive and highly vulnerable ecosystems against rapid changes due to increased human activities and other factors (De La Cruz, 2021). One of the biggest risks and environmental problems of the 21st century facing these areas is sea level rise due to global climate change (Nicholls & Cazenave, 2010; El-Shihy ve Ezquiaga, 2019; Kurt & Li, 2020). More than 10% of the world's population lives on the coasts (Şahin, Navruz & Yılmaz, 2018) and 90% of the largest cities are located by the water (Cosgrave, 2017). In this respect, low-elevation coastal zones along the world's coastline that are less than 10 metres from the coastal boundary and defined as land area contiguous are expected to be affected by climate change (McGranahan, Balk & Anderson, 2007).

In Türkiye, 28 provinces are located directly on the coastal areas (Kurt & Li, 2020). The total area of these coastal cities is 220,447 km² and the total population has been determined as approximately 46 million as of 2020 (Yaman Kocadağlı, 2022). Türkiye's coastal areas are primarily used for public physical activities such as settlement, tourism, sports, recreation and transport (Kurt & Li, 2020; Serim, Karataş, Çırak, Yörür & Kılıç, 2022). According to the calculated morphological values of the coastal cities of Türkiye, the city with the largest urban settled area is İstanbul and the city with the smallest is Sinop. When the open green space utilisation of Türkiye's coasts is examined, the highest city is İstanbul and the lowest cities are Giresun and Çanakkale (Kahraman & Aydın, 2016). In this respect, it is likely that climate change will affect these and other coastal areas of Türkiye where human settlements and activities are intensively realised (Şahin, Navruz & Yılmaz, 2018; Kurt & Li, 2020).

For this reason, floating renewable energy systems are usable and developable technologies for reducing the effects of global climate change in intensively used coastal areas, increasing renewable energy production against fossil fuel use and making sustainable coastal arrangements (Jacobson, Delucchi, Bazouin, Bauer, Heavey, Fisher, Morris, Piekutowski, Vencill & Yeskoo, 2015; Cesur, Gül & Ay, 2018; Cesur Durmaz & Üçgül, 2023; Martinez & Iglesias, 2024).

Renewable energy systems are necessary for the protection of natural areas and ecological balance, human health and the continuity of living life. Countries attach importance to renewable energy with the idea of reducing the use of fossil-based resources, increasing green energy production and achieving a livable world future (Cesur Durmaz & Üçgül, 2023). Renewable energy sources are classified as solar energy, wind energy, water-based energy sources (hydro energy, wave energy, tidal energy, ocean energy, current energy), geothermal energy, biomass energy and hydrogen energy (Üçgül & Elibüyük, 2016).

Today, when we look at the world examples, renewable energy systems widely applied in terrestrial areas, are also developing on the seas thanks to floating structure systems. Floating energy sources such as solar, wind, wave, current, thermal provide alternative energy supply for coastal areas and are used appropriately.

Some of the largest floating solar power plants projects in the world, which are under construction or completed according to their capacities, are Saemangeum floating solar energy project (South Korea), Omkareshwar Dam floating solar farm (India), Hangzhou Fengling Electricity Science Technology's solar

farm (China) and Cirata Reservoir floating photovoltaic power project (Indonesia) (Şenli, 2023). The floating wind platform developed by EnerOcean and W2Power is the first multi-turbine floating solution in the world to be tested offshore (EnerOCEAN, 2019). The InSPIRE project, developed in partnership with TechnipFMC and Bombora, is a floating platform system that can generate wave + wind energy (Bombora, 2024). A wave energy converter that can periodically move up and down in sea waves has been designed by FDN company (FDN, 2016). Simec Atlantis Energy provides installed capacity of up to 2 MW with its SeaGen 'S' tidal and bottom current turbine (Jackson & Persoons, 2012).

When the world examples are examined, it is understood that different floating renewable energy structures are used in mega sizes and are generally constructed in offshore. When analysed in terms of Türkiye, there are mostly projects where floating solar energy structures are installed in stagnant water areas such as rivers, lakes and ponds (Gökmener, Çiçek, Oğuz, Haspolat, Melek & Devenci, 2023). Azmak 2 'Hydroelectric Power Plants + Floating Solar Power Plants Project' and Büyükçekmece 'Floating Solar Power Plants Project' are among the first examples (Bulut, Kaplanoğlu & Geylani, 2018; ASKİ, 2023).

However, the development of hybrid renewable energy systems on smaller floating structures will make it possible to generate energy even in different climatic conditions (Qu, Yao & Du, 2021) and to apply it to near coastal areas. In this way, by increasing the applicability of these technologies in the coastal areas of Türkiye, it will be possible to meet the energy needs, to increase environmental awareness in recreation areas, to reduce the ecological footprint, to support sustainability and raise social awareness in the fight against global warming.

In this study, floating renewable energy structure systems was discussed in order to meet the energy needs of Türkiye's urban coastal areas from renewable energy sources and to increase their use especially in narrow coastal areas. In this respect, the policies and legislative dimensions for offshore installations in Türkiye was analysed. The basic structural design principles of floating renewable energy systems and technical specifications of energy systems was investigated. By mentioning the hybrid floating renewable energy design example proposed in the "Sustainable Floating Urban Park Model: The Case of Fethiye" doctoral thesis, evaluations were made in terms of the development of floating energy installations in the coastal areas of Türkiye. As a result, suggestions for its applicability in Türkiye's coastal areas was presented.

2. Management Policies and Legislative Status of Floating Renewable Energy Structure Systems in Türkiye

Türkiye is a country dependent on foreign energy sources to meet its energy demand by approximately 74%. For this reason, the use of renewable energy resources is of great importance in Türkiye (T.C. Dışişleri Bakanlığı, 2022). In accordance with the National Energy Policy framework adopted in 2017, Türkiye has prioritised increasing domestic and renewable energy resources (Emeksiz & Fındık, 2021). By the end of 2022, production from renewable sources in Türkiye constituted for 54% of the total installed capacity (T.C. Dışişleri Bakanlığı, 2022).

If floating renewable energy resources are examined at the scale of Türkiye; it is seen that resources such as solar, wind, wave, tide, current have started to be utilised (Emeksiz & Fındık, 2021). According to the Türkiye Solar Energy Potential Atlas, the average daily sunshine duration is 7.5 to 8.5 hours/day and the average total radiation intensity is calculated as 4.18 kWh/m²-day (MGM, 2024; Emeksiz & Fındık, 2021). In terms of offshore wind energy potential, Türkiye has a fixed 12 GW and floating 57 GW potential 200 km off the coast (ESMAP, 2019). Türkiye's tidal energy potential is very low and the current energy source is suitable in Çanakkale and İstanbul Straits, but it is not developed due to sea traffic. Wave energy potential is estimated to be 28 GW for a coastal length of 2600 km, excluding the Marmara region (Emeksiz & Fındık, 2021).

Türkiye Ministry of Energy and Natural Resources plans to increase the share of renewable energy sources such as wind and solar in total electricity production in line with its current capabilities and the flexibility it may have in the coming period. Accordingly, the installed capacity is expected to increase to 29.6 GW in wind energy (24.6 GW onshore, 5 GW offshore) and 52.9 GW in solar energy in

2035 (Enerji ve Tabii Kaynaklar Bakanlığı, 2022). However, these projections are not addressed due to technological or economic barriers for marine-based resources such as waves, tides or currents.

In this direction, in Türkiye the Law No. 5346 on the “Law on Utilization of Renewable Energy Sources for the Purpose of Generating Electrical Energy” aims to “Expand the utilization of renewable energy sources for generating electric energy, to benefit from these resources in a secure, economic and qualified manner, to increase the diversification of energy resources, to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, to assess waste products, to protect the environment and to develop the related manufacturing industries for realizing these objectives” (Yenilenebilir Enerji Kaynaklarının Elektrik Enerjisi Üretimi Amaçlı Kullanımına İlişkin Kanun, 2005).

In the Regulation on the “Güneş Enerjisine Dayalı Elektrik Üretimi Başvurularının Teknik Değerlendirmesi Hakkında Yönetmelik” dated 30/06/2017; “The procedures and principles regarding the formation of the technical opinion to be given on the applications made based on solar energy in order to ensure the effective and efficient use of solar energy in the production of electrical energy have been determined” (Güneş Enerjisine Dayalı Elektrik Üretimi Başvurularının Teknik Değerlendirmesi Hakkında Yönetmelik, 2017).

In the Regulation on “Rüzgar Kaynağına Dayalı Elektrik Üretimi Başvurularının Teknik Değerlendirmesi Hakkında Yönetmelik” dated 20/10/2015; “To ensure the effective and efficient use of wind energy in electrical energy generation, to make technical evaluations of pre-licence or unlicensed electricity generation applications made based on wind resource, to make technical evaluations of pre-licensed, licensed or unlicensed projects whose technical evaluations have been concluded positively, the procedures and principles regarding the issuance of the letter of conformity regarding the change of coordinates, capacity increases and change requests regarding turbine technical specifications have been determined.” (Rüzgar Kaynağına Dayalı Elektrik Üretimi Başvurularının Teknik Değerlendirmesi Hakkında Yönetmelik, 2015).

In order to increase the use of renewable energy in Türkiye, the Yenilenebilir Enerji Destekleme Mekanizması (YEKDEM), support for domestically manufactured components used in facilities generating electricity from renewable energy sources (Yerli Aksam), and competitions to determine of Yenilenebilir Enerji Kaynak Alanları (YEKA) are implemented (Albayrak, 2024).

Accordingly, the purpose of the “Yenilenebilir Enerji Kaynak Alanları Yönetmeliği / YEKA Regulation” dated 09/10/2016 is “to use renewable energy resources effectively by creating renewable energy resource areas in public and treasury real estates and privately owned real estates, to realise investments rapidly by allocating these areas to investors, to ensure that advanced technology components used in electrical energy generation facilities based on renewable energy resources are produced domestically or procured domestically, and to contribute to the transfer of technology” (Yenilenebilir Enerji Kaynak Alanları Yönetmeliği, 2016). Within the scope of the Regulation, capacity allocation competitions are held on the areas called YEKA (Kütükcü & Yalılı, 2022).

However, in the Law No. 5346 and YEKA Regulation, the areas declared as YEKA are defined as “public and treasury territory and immovables subject to private ownership”. In this context, it is seen that the areas declared as YEKA refer to onshore installations (Kütükcü & Yalılı, 2022). For this reason, in the Law on the “Maden Kanunu ile Bazı Kanunlarda Değişiklik Yapılmasına Dair Kanun” dated 02/05/2024 and in the title of Article 6 of the Coastal Law No. 3621 the phrase “in the sea” was changed as “in water areas”. At the same time, the phrases “Renewable energy production plants can be established in seas, dam lakes, artificial lakes and natural lakes declared as renewable energy resource areas by the Ministry of Energy and Natural Resources, excluding reservoirs and wetlands where drinking water is supplied and coasts and shorelines within the scope of this Law, without making a zoning plan” were added (Maden Kanunu ile Bazı Kanunlarda Değişiklik Yapılmasına Dair Kanun, 2024).

In Türkiye, domestic and renewable energy resources are more than sufficient to meet the country's needs in terms of electrical energy generation, provided that the right policies are followed (Kütükcü & Yalılı, 2022). In this regard, studies are ongoing to reduce external dependency on energy, increase

the use of local resources and increase the share of renewable energy resources (T.C. Dışişleri Bakanlığı, 2022).

In the Strategic Plan 2024-2028 of the Ministry of Energy and Natural Resources, 7 objectives and 31 targets were determined with the principle of sustainability and nationality for the increasing need for energy and natural resources, and 113 performance indicators were established for these targets. It is envisaged to increase the share of electricity generation based on renewable energy resources in total generation from 43% to 50%. In order to utilise offshore renewable energy resources in this direction, strategic decisions were taken stating that studies should be carried out for the installation of renewable energy plants such as offshore wind power plants and floating solar power plants (Enerji ve Tabii Kaynaklar Bakanlığı, 2024). In this regard, it is also seen that Turkey has begun to make political decisions to increase floating renewable energy installations.

3. Technical Specifications for the Design of Hybrid Floating Renewable Energy Structure Systems

The energy required for coastal settlements, public areas, or coastal parks in Turkey's coastal areas can be met from modular floating renewable energy structures that are compatible with the coastal edge line and have high aesthetic quality. In this respect, floating carrier foundation structure design and renewable energy system technical details were analysed. In addition, the floating energy power plant developed as a proposal in the "Sustainable Floating Urban Park Model: The Case of Fethiye" doctoral thesis study was given as an example.

3.1. Design concept and principles of floating renewable energy foundation structure system

It is important that floating renewable energy foundation system remain stable on the water and do not hinder energy production efficiency. In this respect, the building materials used should be durable, long-lasting, recyclable and have features that minimise environmental problems.

When the materials used in the design of floating foundation structure are analysed, although regarding durability and stability concrete has high-pressure strength, nevertheless it has low-tensile one. Steel is implanted inside the concrete structure to reinforce the tensile strength. When the concrete coating thickness is increased to prevent corrosion of the steel, the weight of the structure also increases. For this reason, Fibre Reinforced Concrete applications are developing (El-Shihy & Ezquiaga, 2019).

Expanded Polystyrene Concrete floating structure designs combined with concrete and foam are lightweight, stable and flexible to the movement of the structure (Koekoek, 2010). At the same time, it is environmentally friendly, has zero carbon footprint and supports sustainability features (Vu, 2016). In this respect, it is preferred more in floating foundation structures.

Other factors to be taken into consideration when determining floating renewable energy structures are listed below.

- Floating renewable energy foundation structures are in constant movement in the wave loads marine environment. This situation reduces or changes the energy production (Claus & López, 2022). Therefore, the floating structure must be able to remain stable and ensure structural safety.
- Since floating energy structures are exposed to wind and wave loads, attention should be paid to corrosion when selecting the construction materials (Claus & López, 2022). Waterproof concrete and steel with appropriate standard properties should be used to prevent corrosion of steel reinforcement in concrete.
- Considering natural and environmental factors, the materials used should have ecological properties and should not contain environmental pollutants. In this respect, sustainable building materials with high recycling rates should be preferred.
- The use of local materials should also be considered in order to reduce the cost of floating energy structures.

In the doctoral thesis study titled Sustainable Floating Urban Park Model: The Case of Fethiye, the floating power plant concrete foundation structure system was designed in a hexagonal form with a center hollow in order not to block the sunlight required for underwater ecosystems. EPS foam filled concrete columns with a diameter of 150 cm and a length of 400 cm were placed at the corners of the floating structure in order to increase the buoyancy and to keep the module balanced in the water. The column length was determined by considering the wind turbine height (500 cm and 1000 cm). These columns were placed on the base of the main body consisting of 150 cm high EPS foam filled concrete material. The six columns were connected to each other from top and bottom with steel connection elements. A cross connection was provided between all opposing columns and the centre. Natural looking laminated wood was used as the covering material on the upper part (Table 1).

Table 1. Example of floating renewable energy foundation structure design

Foundation structure area	205 m ²	Hexagonal steel column connection
Main body	150 cm	Cross steel column connection
Foundation sub-column	150 x 400 cm	Centre steel column connection

In order to keep the modules stable under the effect of waves and to prevent displacement, they were connected to the underwater concrete blocks with a steel anchor system.

3.2. Technical specifications of floating renewable energy systems

The hybrid use of renewable energy systems installed on floating structures provides better results in different climatic conditions. In this respect, solar energy, wind energy and wave energy are emerging as technologies that are being used in hybrid use (Habibi, 2015).

Floating solar energy is generally limited to inland water bodies such as lakes, ponds or hydroelectric dam reservoirs that do not have wave motions. The float consists of the PV modules and their supporting system, which supports the weight of the modules and transmits the stresses on the float, electrical equipment, mooring and anchoring elements (Oliveira-Pinto & Stokkermans, 2020).

Wind energy is divided into two types according to the rotation axes of the turbines: horizontal axis and vertical axis. Horizontal axis wind turbines are systems that have high noise generate and can cause negative environmental effects. Vertical axis wind turbines are easy to manufacture and install, produce less noise and can operate in omni-directional winds. In addition, vertical turbines can generate electrical power at low wind speeds and create more cost-effective performance (Rajpar, Ali, Eladwi & Bashir, 2021).

Since wave energy is affected by wind pressures and physical conditions, wave height, wave length and wave period determine the energy to be obtained. Therefore, electricity generation with wave energy differs from other renewable energy sources. In general, wave energy converters are divided into three categories as oscillating water column, overtopping devices and wave activated bodies (Amir, Sharip, Muzanni & Anuar, 2016).

In the doctoral thesis study titled Sustainable Floating Urban Park Model: The Case of Fethiye, the solar, wind and wave energy systems were used considering the carrying capacity of the floating structure. For the solar energy panel, 380 W, high nominal power and monocrystalline 72-cell panel system of Anchor by Panasonic was preferred (Anchor by Panasonic, 2022). Since wind energy is an important input in renewable energy production, a vertical axis Senwei Energy Technology wind

turbine with high nominal power was used (Senwei Energy Technology, 2022). Two different mast lengths of 500 cm and 1000 cm were determined in order to benefit optimally from the wind angle and the turbine placement was positioned so as not to block the wind angle. For the wave energy converter, a floating two-body, multi-point, wave absorber converter described in Guo et al. (2022) was preferred. Since no system suitable for the size of the floating structure and providing energy calculations was found in the literature, the WaveStar C6-600 kW model wave energy converter (WaveStar, 2022) was used scaled down to 1:10, to cover the surroundings of the floating structure. However, an approximate value was taken as a suggestion for wave energy calculation. Technical details of solar, wind and wave energy company products are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Solar, wind and wave energy company product features used on the floating renewable energy structure

SOLAR		WIND		WAVE	
Feature	Monocrystalline	Rotor diameter	4 m	Diameter of the float	600 cm
Weight	22.5 kg	Rotor weight	460 kg	Length of steel arm	1200 cm
Cells	72	Wing length	4 m	Maximum water depth	20 m
Panel size	1985 x 1003 x 40 mm	Commissioning wind speed	2 m/sec	Maximum wave height	8 m
Nominal power	380 Wp	Nominal power	10 kW	Nominal power	30 kW

In the doctoral thesis study titled Sustainable Floating Urban Park Model: The Case Of Fethiye, the power values of the hybrid floating energy plant were calculated approximately. The total power calculations of solar, wind and wave energy systems are given in Table 3.

Table 3. Total power calculations of solar, wind and wave energy systems

Solar Energy		Wind Energy	
Type	PV	Type	Darrieus Savonius
Power	380 Wp	Power	10 kW
Number	528	Number	46
Total Installed Power	~200 kW	Total Installed Power	460 kW

Wave Energy		Hybrid Power Plant	
Type	Reciprocating Converter	Solar energy TIC	200 kW
Power	1 kW	Wind energy TIC	460 kW
Number	206 kW	Wave energy TIC	206 kW
Total Installed	206 kW	TOTAL	866 kW
Capacity (TIC)			

As a result of the approximate power calculations obtained regardless of the ambient conditions, a total value of 866 kW was reached. However, since the floating energy structure was developed as a proposal, energy potential calculations were not performed.

4. Evaluation and Discussion of Hybrid Floating Renewable Energy Plant Example

Floating energy structures can be implemented in protected coastal regions or partially sheltered waters and offshore areas (Martinez & Iglesias, 2024). Coastal areas and the open seas provide the large area utilization needed for renewable energy production and support sustainable energy production. Floating energy systems have many environmental, economic and technological advantages in coastal areas.

Floating energy structures have advantages such as preventing land loss and deforestation (Bulut et al., 2018; Dünya Bankası Grubu, ESMAP & SERIS, 2019; Şenli, 2023), preventing soil pollution and erosion, preventing damage to bird migration routes and ambient creatures, reducing ecological destruction (Ferrer Gisbert, Ferrán Gozávez, Redón Santafé, Ferrer Gisbert, Sánchez Romero & Torregrosa Soler, 2013), obtaining relatively lower ambient temperature required for photovoltaic systems (Ferrer Gisbert et al., 2013; Bulut et al., 2018; Claus & López, 2022; Şenli, 2023). These advantages are important factors for the development of floating energy systems and increasing their application areas.

In this respect, evaluations were made regarding the foundation structural features, energy systems and sustainability dimensions in terms of the development of hybrid floating renewable energy structure systems in the coastal areas of Türkiye.

Evaluation and discussion of the floating foundation structure findings:

Floating structures are functional and can be constructed easily and quickly (Kizilova, 2019). Additionally, it has an easy transport feature (Huang et al., 2023). In this respect, the fact that floating energy systems consist of modular structures provides easy installation, relocation and transportation (Kizilova, 2019).

Sea water causes damage to the durability and functionality of floating structures, photovoltaic systems and electrical equipment. Therefore, it is necessary to take anti-corrosion measures and determine the appropriate structural form (Claus & López, 2022; Huang, Tang, Chen, Chen & Jiang, 2023). The floating renewable energy carrier base structure is made of EPS foam filled concrete material, which is also mentioned in different literature applications, and is one of the materials that will reduce the corrosion threat (El-Shihy ve Ezquiaga, 2019; Amphibious Houses, 2021; Engineered Foam Products, 2021; STYRO EPS, 2021).

Land reclamation implemented to obtain land area in coastal cities with narrow coastlines creates high costs for national economies (El-Shihy & Ezquiaga, 2019). However, the installation of energy systems on floating modular structures significantly reduces the cost and prevents the change of coastal form.

Floating energy structures do not require site preparation (Dünya Bankası Grubu et al., 2019). In this respect, the development of floating energy structure systems facilitates their integration into Türkiye's coastal areas.

Evaluation and discussion of the hybrid energy systems findings:

It is possible to generate energy from solar, wind, waves, currents and tidal conditions with different floating energy systems (Chen & Wu, 2024). With a hybrid floating power plant using solar, wind and wave systems, the sustainability of energy production becomes possible in all climatic conditions.

Floating energy installations make it possible to generate clean energy on existing water resources without causing any loss of agricultural or forest land in offshore environments (Claus & López, 2022; Şenli, 2023).

The installation of onshore solar panels can damage valuable land that can be used for agriculture, mining, tourism and other activities (Huang et al., 2023). Floating PV systems prevent land use conflicts, provide an innovative and sustainable approach.

Floating photovoltaic structures significantly reduce evaporation by reducing the water surface temperature (Huang et al., 2023). In this respect, the development of floating energy structure systems contributes to the improvement of the environment by preventing evaporation in water resources.

The cooling effect of water ensures PV systems operate more efficiently (Oliveira-Pinto & Stokkermans, 2020; Claus & López, 2022; Huang et al., 2023; Martinez & Iglesias, 2024). Thanks to the development of floating energy structures, energy performance increases compared to land installations.

Floating photovoltaic systems are difficult to clean and maintain, so malfunctions may occur within the system (Huang et al., 2023). The installation of PV systems on floating structure modules offers easier maintenance and cleaning.

The greater flexibility and scalability of offshore wind energy increases energy efficiency and reduces environmental impact compared to onshore installations (Hong, McMorland, Zhang, Collu & Halse, 2024). In this way, visual and noise distractions are eliminated.

Floating offshore wind turbines experience more severe environmental loads than fixed offshore wind turbines (Hong, 2024). The use and positioning of wind turbines suitable for the size of the floating structure reduces the environmental loads.

Evaluation and discussion of the floating energy structures' sustainability aspects:

Floating energy systems create 5% less environmental impact than fossil resources and generate energy by protecting underwater reservoirs (Kizilova, 2019). Thanks to the power to be generated from the floating energy structure, a solution for efficient and sustainable energy production suitable for environmental conditions is provided.

If the application dimensions of floating energy systems are studied by the relevant disciplines, it will be easier to integrate them into the coastal areas of Türkiye. In this way, renewable energy production that is integrated with coastal ecosystems and considers environmental sustainability is possible.

The production of floating energy structures for coastal areas allows the energy required to be met independently of the grid. Thus, by supporting economic development in coastal areas and increasing the use of renewable energy resources, Türkiye's full independence in energy supply is contributed.

At the same time, it is expected that the carbon footprint will be significantly reduced if the application areas are increased throughout Türkiye.

5. Conclusion and Suggestions

Renewable energy sources are important technologies that provide solutions to the global warming problem. Due to the effects of the global climate crisis, there is a significant growth in land installations of solar and wind energy in the world. However, the scarcity and high price of available land needed for renewable energy installations in coastal cities constitute an obstacle to expansion in coastal areas (Martinez & Iglesias, 2024). In this context, offshore or nearshore environments provide large area utilisation for renewable energy production and emerge as an alternative (El-Shihy ve Ezquiaga, 2019; Martinez & Iglesias, 2024).

While a large portion of energy production in Türkiye comes from fossil resources, floating solar power plant applications on dam lakes are also frequently encountered today (Şenli, 2023). The fact that Türkiye is surrounded by seas on three sides and there are densely populated urban settlements in coastal areas indicates that renewable energy generation should be increased on the seas as well. However, Türkiye's coastal areas generally have narrow borders and the open lands needed for renewable energy installations are insufficient. For this reason, in coastal areas with intensive energy consumption, energy needs are generally met from the grid, increasing public costs. However, the production of different types and sizes of hybrid floating renewable energy technologies and establishing relations them with coastal areas will support Türkiye's green energy generation and facilitate the achievement of sustainability goals.

As a result, hybrid floating renewable energy structures are necessary to meet the energy needs in Türkiye's coastal areas, as they will minimise environmental damage and provide sustainable energy supply. At the same time, it creates advantages that play an important role in reducing Türkiye's ecological footprint, provide coastal cities with a new added value and identity in terms of energy, increase social environmental consciousness and awareness, and contribute to the economy. At this point, new decisions are being made in the legislation regarding offshore installations in our country and strategic targets and goals are being determined in energy generation. However, since there are no hybrid combinations of floating energy systems in Türkiye today, it is necessary to study the developments and innovative solutions in floating renewable energy technology in the future. In order to increase the applicability of floating energy systems for Türkiye, the following recommendations should be considered.

- Hybrid renewable energy systems should be decided by taking into account factors such as Türkiye's climatic characteristics, environmental conditions and social dimensions.
- Sustainability criteria should be taken into consideration when determining the material use, structural form and size of floating energy structure modules.
- Numerical analysis methods should be developed for optimum location selection of floating energy structures.
- Cost reports should be prepared as an example for future studies.
- R&D and scientific activities should be carried out for the development of floating renewable energy structures.
- In order to increase its use in coastal areas of Türkiye, all design and implementation stages should be detailed in the laws and regulations.

Acknowledgments and Information Note

This article, Süleyman Demirel University Graduate School of Natural and Applied Sciences completed at the Department of Civil Engineering was produced from the doctoral thesis "Sustainable Floating

Urban Park Model: The Case of Fethiye". The Council of Higher Education (CoHE) (YÖK) 100/2000 doctoral program was prepared within the scope of the thematic area of "Sustainable Building Materials and Technologies". Supported by SDU Scientific Research Projects Coordination Unit (BAP) (Project No. FDK-2019-7018). The article complies with national and international research and publication ethics. Ethics Committee approval was not required for the study.

Author Contribution and Conflict of Interest Disclosure Information

All authors contributed equally to the article. There is no conflict of interest.

References

- Albayrak, M. (2024). Yenilenebilir enerji yatırımları ve destekleme mekanizmaları. Access Address (20.11.2024): https://ticaret.gov.tr/data/65dc9d3113b8762768385d66/ETKB%20SKDM%20Sunum-Yenilenebilir%20Enerji_23022024.pdf
- Amir, M. A. U., Sharip, R. M., Muzanni, M. A. & Anuar, H. A. (2016). Wave energy convertors (WEC): A review of the technology and power generation. *International Conference on Mathematics, Engineering and Industrial Applications, Vol. 1775, No: 1*. AIP Publishing. doi: 10.1063/1.4965220. Access Address (18.11.2024): <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4965220>
- Amphibious Houses. (2021). Coastal engineering - Amphibious housing. Access Address (20.10.2021): <http://amphibioushomes.weebly.com/floating-foundations--bases.html>
- Anchor by Panasonic. (2022). Access Address (12.01.2022): <https://lstr.panasonic.com/tr/urunler/detay/395w-mono-perc-solar-module-2684/>
- ASKİ. (2023). Türkiye’de ilk: ASKİ, baraj üzerinde yüzer GES kurarak elektrik üretecek. Access Address (18.11.2024): <https://www.aski.gov.tr/tr/HABER/Turk%C4%B1yede-ilk-Ask%C4%B1-Baraj-Uzer%C4%B1nde-Yuzer-Ges-Kurarak-Elektr%C4%B1k-Uretecek/569>
- Avcı, S. (2017). Kıyı Alanlarının Kullanımında Beşerî Faktörler. H. Turoğlu ve H. Yiğitbaşıoğlu (Ed.). *Yasal ve Bilimsel Boyutları ile Kıyı. Jeomorfoloji Derneği Yayını (Temmuz, 2017), No.1 (s. 117-146)*. ISBN: 978-605-67576-0-0. İstanbul: Çantay.
- Bombora. (2024). InSpire project – Integrated wave and wind floating platform. Access Address (14.11.2024): <https://www.inspireoffshoreenergy.com/>
- Bulut, M., Kaplanoğlu, İ. & Geylani, V. (2018). Dünyada hidro yüzer GES projelerinin gelişimi ve Türkiye’deki potansiyeli. *Güç Sistemleri Konferansı* (p. 13-18). Ankara, Türkiye. Access Address (07.11.2024): <https://www.cigareturkiye.org.tr/gsk2018/bildiri/03.ID-22.pdf>
- Cesur Durmaz, B. & Üçgül, İ. (2023). Evaluation of floating renewable energy potential for sustainable energy in Türkiye. *Journal of the Institute of Science and Technology*, 13(2), 1085-1100. Access Address (05.11.2024): <https://doi.org/10.21597/jist.1089488>
- Cesur, B., Gül, A. & Ay, Z. (2018). Kıyı kullanımlarında yüzen platform üzeri çok amaçlı kent parkı tasarım yaklaşımı. *9. Kıyı Mühendisliği Sempozyumu* (p. 400-412). Adana, Türkiye. Access Address (02.11.2024): https://eski.imo.org.tr/resimler/ekutuphane/pdf/18341_53_13.pdf
- Chen, P. & Wu, D. (2024). A review of hybrid wave-tidal energy conversion technology. *Ocean Engineering*, 303, 117684. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oceaneng.2024.117684>
- Claus, R. & López, M. (2022). Key issues in the design of floating photovoltaic structures for the marine environment. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 164, 112502. Access Address (10.11.2024): <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2022.112502>
- Cosgrave, E. (2017). The future of floating cities – and the realities. Access Address (16.12.2019): <https://www.bbc.com/future/article/20171128-the-future-of-floating-cities-and-the-realities>
- De La Cruz, P. M. C. (2021). The knowledge status of coastal and marine ecosystem services challenges, limitations and lessons learned from the application of the ecosystem services approach in

management. *Frontiers in Marine Science* 8:684770.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2021.684770>

- Dünya Bankası Grubu, ESMAP, & SERIS. (2019). Güneşin su ile buluştuğu yer yüzer: güneş piyasası raporu. Washington, ABD, DC: World Bank Group. Access Address (05.11.2021): <https://www.solarbaba.org/wp-content/uploads/bilgi-004-yuzer-ges.pdf>
- El-Shihy, A. A. & Ezquiaga, J. M. (2019). Architectural design concept and guidelines for floating structures for tackling sea level rise impacts on Abu-Qir. *Alexandria Engineering Journal*, 58(2), 507-518. Access Address (05.11.2024): <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aej.2019.05.003>
- Emeksiz, C. & Fındık, M. M. (2021). Sürdürülebilir kalkınma için yenilenebilir enerji kaynaklarının Türkiye ölçeğinde değerlendirilmesi. *Avrupa Bilim ve Teknoloji Dergisi*, (26), 155-164. Access Address (20.11.2024): <https://dergipark.org.tr/en/download/article-file/1809993>
- Enerji ve Tabii Kaynaklar Bakanlığı. (2022). Türkiye ulusal enerji planı. Access Address (20.11.2024): https://enerji.gov.tr/Media/Dizin/EIGM/tr/Raporlar/TUEP/T%C3%BCrkiye_Ulusal_Enerji_Plan%C4%B1.pdf
- Enerji ve Tabii Kaynaklar Bakanlığı. (2024). 2024-2028 Stratejik planı. Access Address (20.11.2024): https://enerji.gov.tr/Media/Dizin/SGB/tr/Kurumsal_Politikalar/ETKB_2024-2028_Stratejik_Planı.pdf
- EnerOcean. (2019). The future of floating. Now. Access Address (14.11.2024): <https://enerocean.com/w2power/>
- Engineered Foam Products. (2021). EPS pontoons. Access Address (20.11.2021): <https://www.engineeredfoamproducts.com/products/eps-pontoons/>
- ESMAP. (2019). Going global: expanding offshore wind to emerging markets. Access Address (20.11.2024): <https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/pt/716891572457609829/pdf/Going-Global-Expanding-Offshore-Wind-To-Emerging-Markets.pdf>
- FDN. (2016). Wave energy converter. Access Address (14.11.2024): <https://www.fdngrupp.nl/energy-converter>
- Ferrer Gisbert, C., Ferrán Gozálviz, J. J., Redón Santafé, M., Ferrer Gisbert, P., Sánchez Romero, F. J. & Torregrosa Soler, J. B. (2013). A new photovoltaic floating cover system for water reservoirs. *Renewable Energy*, 60, 63-70. Access Address (05.11.2024): <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2013.04.007>
- Gökmener, S., Çiçek, D., Oğuz, E., Haspolat, E., Melek, A. & Devenci, M. (2023). Yüzer güneş enerjisi santralleri için uygun yer seçiminde kullanılan kriterler. *10. Kıyı Mühendisliği Sempozyumu* (p. 331-343). İzmir, Türkiye. Access Address (06.11.2024): https://www.researchgate.net/publication/375890908_Yuzer_Gunes_Enerjisi_Santralleri_Icin_Uygun_Yer_Seciminde_Kullanilan_Kriterler
- Güneş Enerjisine Dayalı Elektrik Üretimi Başvurularının Teknik Değerlendirmesi Hakkında Yönetmelik. (2017, 30 06). T.R. Official Gazette (No: 30110). Prime Ministry Printing House, Ankara. Access Address (19.11.2024): <https://www.resmigazete.gov.tr/eskiler/2017/06/20170630-10.htm>
- Habibi, S. (2015). Floating building opportunities for future sustainable development and energy efficiency gains. *Journal of Architectural Engineering Technology*, 4(2), 1-6. Access Address (05.11.2024): https://www.researchgate.net/publication/280922308_Floating_Building_Opportunities_for_Future_Sustainable_Development_and_Energy_Efficiency_Gains
- Hong, S., McMorland, J., Zhang, H., Collu, M. & Halse, K. H. (2024). Floating offshore wind farm installation, challenges and opportunities: A comprehensive survey. *Ocean Engineering*, 304, 117793. Access Address (05.11.2024): <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oceaneng.2024.117793>

- Huang, G., Tang, Y., Chen, X., Chen, M. & Jiang, Y. (2023). A comprehensive review of floating solar plants and potentials for offshore applications. *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, 11(11), 2064. Access Address (05.11.2024): <https://doi.org/10.3390/jmse11112064>
- Jacobson, M. Z., Delucchi, M. A., Bazouin, G., Bauer, Z. A., Heavey, C. C., Fisher, E., Morris, S.B.,...& Yeskoo, T. W. (2015). 100% Clean and renewable wind, water, and sunlight (WWS) all-sector energy roadmaps for the 50 United States. *Energy & Environmental Science*, 8(7), p.107. Access Address (08.11.2024): <https://pubs.rsc.org/en/content/articlelanding/2015/ee/c5ee01283j>
- Jackson, D. & Persoons, T. (2012). Feasibility study and cost-benefit analysis of tidal energy: A case study for Ireland. *Proceedings of the 4th International Conference on Ocean Energy (ICOE)* (pp.1-6). Dublin, Ireland. Access Address (05.11.2024): https://www.researchgate.net/publication/257936291_Feasibility_study_and_cost-benefit_analysis_of_tidal_energy_A_case_study_for_Ireland
- Kahraman, E. D. & Aydın, S. (2016). Deniz seviyesinin yükselmesi tehdidine karşı kıyı kentlerinin morfolojik açıdan kırılabilirlik düzeylerinin belirlenmesi. *TUCAUM Uluslararası Coğrafya Sempozyumu* (p. 675-681). Ankara, Türkiye. Access Address (03.11.2024): https://tucaum.ankara.edu.tr/wp-content/uploads/sites/280/2016/12/Int_semp_AK3.pdf
- Kizilova, S. (2019). Form and functional features of modular floating structures. In *E3S Web of Conferences: Vol. 91*, Article Number: 05013 (p. 1-6). EDP Sciences. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/20199105013>
- Koekoek, M. J. (2010). *Connecting modular floating structures: a general survey and structural design of a modular floating pavilion (Master's thesis)*. Delft University of Technology, Delft. Access Address (05.11.2024): <https://repository.tudelft.nl/record/uuid:33b59201-1718-4dda-98f8-ee16d5b7c023>
- Kurt, S. & Li, X. (2020). Potential impacts of sea level rise on the coasts of Turkey. *Journal of Environment and Earth Science*, 10(5), 40-4. Paper ISSN: 2224-3216, Online ISSN: 2225-0948. Access Address (05.11.2024): <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/327151922.pdf>
- Kütükcü, G. & Yalılı, M. (2022). Deniz üstü rüzgar enerji santrali projelerinde ülke uygulamalarının incelenmesi ve Türkiye için öneriler. *Mühendislik Bilimleri ve Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 4(1), 1-21. Access Address (05.11.2024): <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/download/article-file/2060947>
- Maden Kanunu ile Bazı Kanunlarda Değişiklik Yapılmasına Dair Kanun. (2024). T.R. Official Gazette (No: 7501). Prime Ministry Printing House, Ankara. Access Address (19.11.2024): <https://www.resmigazete.gov.tr/eskiler/2024/05/20240511-1.htm>
- Martinez, A. & Iglesias, G. (2024). Mapping of the levelised cost of energy from floating solar PV in coastal waters of the European Atlantic, North Sea and Baltic Sea. *Solar Energy*, 279, 112809. Access Address (15.11.2024): <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2024.112809>
- McGranahan, G., Balk, D. & Anderson, B. (2007). The rising tide: assessing the risks of climate change and human settlements in low elevation coastal zones. *Environment and Urbanization*, 19(1), 17-37. Access Address (12.11.2024): <https://doi.org/10.1177/0956247807076960>
- MGM. (2024). Türkiye Ortalama Güneşlenme Süresi (1991-2020). Erişim Adresi (25.11.2024) <https://mgm.gov.tr/kurumici/turkiye-guneslenme-suresi.aspx>
- Nicholls, R. J. & Cazenave, A. (2010). Sea-level rise and its impact on coastal zones. *Science*, 328(5985), 1517–1520. Access Address (11.11.2024): <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1185782>
- Oliveira-Pinto, S. & Stokkermans, J. (2020). Marine floating solar plants: An overview of potential, challenges and feasibility. *Maritime Engineering*, 173(4), 120-135. Access Address (13.11.2024): <https://doi.org/10.1680/jmaen.2020.10>

- Qu, X., Yao, Y. & Du, J. (2021). Conceptual design and hydrodynamic performance of a modular hybrid floating foundation. *Energies*, 14(22), 7605. Access Address (17.11.2024): <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14227605>
- Rajpar, A. H., Ali, I., Eladwi, A. E. & Bashir, M. B. A. (2021). Recent development in the design of wind deflectors for vertical axis wind turbine: A review. *Energies*, 14(16), 5140. Access Address (15.11.2024): <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14165140>
- Rüzgar Kaynağına Dayalı Elektrik Üretimi Başvurularının Teknik Değerlendirmesi Hakkında Yönetmelik. (2015). T.R. Official Gazette (No: 29508). Prime Ministry Printing House, Ankara. Access Address (19.11.2024): <https://resmigazete.gov.tr/eskiler/2015/10/20151020-2.htm>
- Senwei Energy Technology. (2022). Access Address (08.01.2022): <https://www.windpowercn.com/>
- Serim, R. B., Karataş, N., Çırak, A. A., Yörür, N. & Kılıç, S. E. (2022). Kıyı kanunundaki değişimlerin kıyı yerleşmelerindeki arazi kullanım değişimine etkisi: Kuşadası merkez örneği. *Planlama Dergisi*, 32(1), 57-76. Access Address (12.11.2024): <https://planlamadergisi.org/jvi.aspx?pdır=planlama&plng=tur&un=PLAN-98598>
- STYRO EPS. (2021). Styro EPS for pontoon and buoy. Access Address (20.11.2021): <https://www.styrouae.com/insulation-and-construction/styro-eps-for-pontoon-and-buoy/>
- Şahin, A., Navruz, M. & Yılmaz, F. H. (2018, 25.10). Küresel ısınmaya dayanıklı kentler; Hollanda kentleri üzerine bir değerlendirme. *Uluslararası Kamu Yönetimi Sempozyumu* (s. 1-11). Kırıkkale, Türkiye. Access Address (14.11.2021): https://www.researchgate.net/publication/330997411_KURESEL_ISINMAYA_DAYANIKLI_KENTLER_HOLLANDA_KENTLERI_UZERINDEN_BIR_DEGERLENDIRME
- Şenli, H. (2023). Yüzen güneş enerjisi sistemlerinin incelenmesi, çevresel katkıları ve Türkiye'deki barajların yüzen güneş enerjisi potansiyeli. *International Journal of Advances in Engineering and Pure Sciences*, 35(4), 418-427. Access Address (16.11.2024): <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/download/article-file/2994895>
- T.C. Dışişleri Bakanlığı. (2022). Türkiye'nin Uluslararası Enerji Stratejisi. Access Address (16.11.2024): https://www.mfa.gov.tr/turkiye_nin-enerji-stratejisi.tr.mfa
- Üçgül, İ. & Elibüyük, U. (2016). Yenilenebilir ve alternatif enerji çeşitleri. Aysel Aydın Kocaeren (Ed.). *Çevre ve Enerji*. Nobel Akademik Yayıncılık (Şubat, 2016), (p. 222-307).
- WaveStar. (2022). Wavestar prototype at Roshage. Performance data for ForskVE Project No:2009-1-10305 phase 1 & 2, January 2013, 23p.
- Vu, P. L. (2016). *Floating architecture: Hawaii's response to sea level rise* (Ph.D. thesis). University of Hawai'i At Mānoa, Architecture Department. Access Address (14.11.2024): <https://scholarspace.manoa.hawaii.edu/items/49d0c371-f1f0-47ed-bb4b-034941e5457d>
- Yaman Kocadağlı, A. (2022). Coastal areas in the spatial distribution of population in Türkiye. *Eurasian Academy of Sciences Social Sciences Journal*, 43, 1-12. Access Address (17.11.2024): <https://eurasianacademy.org/index.php/socialsciences/issue/view/2022-43>
- Yenilenebilir Enerji Kaynak Alanları Yönetmeliği. (2016, 09 10). T.R. Official Gazette (No: 29852). Prime Ministry Printing House, Ankara. Access Address (19.11.2024): <https://mevzuat.gov.tr/mevzuat?MevzuatNo=22923&MevzuatTur=7&MevzuatTertip=5>
- Yenilenebilir Enerji Kaynaklarının Elektrik Enerjisi Üretimi Amaçlı Kullanımına İlişkin Kanun. (2005, 10 05). T.R. Official Gazette (No: 5346). Prime Ministry Printing House, Ankara. Access Address (19.11.2024): <https://www.mevzuat.gov.tr/mevzuatmetin/1.5.5346.pdf>

